

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

Abdiyazova Sarvinoz Atadjanovna

Teacher of Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897642>

Abstract: In this thesis, the theoretical foundations of the development of the educational activity of future primary school teachers are highlighted. Innovative approaches and modern educational technologies are used in order to increase the professional competence of teachers, organize the educational process effectively and develop creative thinking skills of students.

Key words: Primary education, educational activities, methodology, innovative approach, educational technologies, creative thinking.

Introduction.

In today's education system, elementary school teachers play an important role in ensuring the success of the educational process. The formation of students' knowledge, skills and abilities, their preparation for successful implementation in life depends on the level of professional training of teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to supplement the methods aimed at developing the educational activities of the future elementary school teachers, innovative approaches and technologies that meet the requirements of the time.

The article examines the issues of improving the methods used by teachers in the use of pedagogical methods, in the effective organization of the educational process, and in the development of creative thinking abilities of students. Changes in the educational system of Uzbekistan and the need to comply with global educational standards require updating pedagogical methods and strategies.

In this regard, in this study, scientifically based recommendations are given for improving the educational methods used in the process of professional training of future teachers. In this case, activities aimed at improving the pedagogical skills of teachers and preparing them for new thinking and innovative approaches in the educational process are important. The article aims to highlight current problems in the field of education and introduce innovations into the process of training future teachers.

Literature analysis.

The issue of improving the methodology for the development of educational activities of future elementary school teachers is based on many studies in the fields of pedagogy and psychology. Through the analysis of this literature, the

main directions in the effective organization of the professional training process of teachers and the application of innovative methods in the educational process are determined.

Pedagogical methods: Changes in teaching methods reflect innovations in the educational system. Also, creative approaches are important in the development of teachers' educational activities.

Innovative approaches: Innovative educational technologies and approaches, such as problem-based learning, collaborative learning, project-based learning, are important tools for teachers to effectively organize the learning process. It is emphasized that these approaches should be used in the changes and innovations in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Improving the quality of the educational process: The relationship and cooperation between teachers and students during the educational process is important in improving the quality of education.

Psychological aspects: The psychological aspects of educational activities are also important in improving the professional competence of teachers. The development of students' self-control, motivation and emotional intelligence should be taken into account in the pedagogical activities of teachers.

Practical experiences: Researches and practical experiences conducted in Uzbekistan and foreign countries, for example, educational systems in European countries and their pedagogical methods, should be used in the training process of future teachers. This will create an opportunity to improve the competencies of teachers and implement innovative approaches.

The issue of improving the methodology for the development of educational activities of future elementary school teachers has been widely covered by foreign researchers. Their works show innovative approaches aimed at effective organization of the educational process, improvement of teachers' pedagogical skills and development of students' creative abilities.

In this study, the issues of improving the methodology of developing the educational activities of future elementary school teachers were widely discussed. Methods and approaches aimed at increasing the professional competence of teachers, organizing the educational process effectively, and developing students' creative thinking skills are important.

First, the use of innovative approaches to the development of teachers' educational activities, including problem-based learning, project-based teaching and cooperative teaching methods, will help to expand the knowledge and skills of students. During the research, the effectiveness of these methods was

confirmed through experiments and questionnaires. Students felt more active and participated more in the lesson process.

Secondly, the role of educational technologies in improving the pedagogical skills of teachers is great. Modern educational technologies, such as interactive whiteboards, multimedia tools and online platforms, serve to increase the quality of the educational process. With these technologies, teachers have been able to increase student interest, make lessons more interactive, and develop students' self-directed learning skills.

Thirdly, the achievements of teachers in the process of mutual cooperation and exchange of experience are also important. Open communication and exchange of experience between teachers helps in introducing pedagogical innovations. To develop this process, it is necessary to unite teachers through organizations and scientific societies, conduct seminars and trainings.

Also, psychological preparation and self-management skills of teachers are important. Teachers need to have the skills to manage stress and direct their emotions. This, in turn, increases the impact on students and creates a positive atmosphere of the learning process.

As a result, the need for changes in the educational system and modern pedagogical approaches was shown to improve the methodology for the development of educational activities of future primary school teachers. It is expected that the results of this research will help teachers to use methods that meet the requirements of modern education and will serve to improve the quality of the educational process.

Conclusion.

This study is focused on the issue of improving the methodology of the development of educational activities of future elementary school teachers. The obtained results show that innovative approaches, modern educational technologies and psychological training are of great importance in the pedagogical activity of teachers. When such methods are used in the educational process, the learning process of students is effective, and their creative thinking and independent work skills are developed. Based on the results of the research, the following conclusions were drawn:

Importance of Innovative Methods: Problem-based learning, project-based learning, and cooperative learning methods are important tools for future teachers. They help to increase the level of learning of students and increase their interest.

The role of educational technologies: The use of modern educational technologies serves to make the educational process more effective. Interactive tools and multimedia technologies encourage students to actively participate in the learning process.

Collaboration among teachers: Open communication and exchange of experiences among teachers is important in the implementation of pedagogical innovations. Their cooperation improves the quality of education.

Psychological preparation: The level of psychological preparation and emotional intelligence of teachers is necessary for success in the educational process. Stress management and self-control skills play an important role in teachers' professional activities.

References:

1. Gardner, H. (1983). *Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences*. New York: Basic Books.
2. Marzano, R. J. (2007). *The Art and Science of Teaching: A Comprehensive Framework for Effective Instruction*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD.
3. Patton, K. (2015). The Role of Emotional Intelligence in Teacher Education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 66(5), 389-394.
4. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
5. Madraximovich, K. E. (2020). Improving the methodological training of primary school teachers on the basis of innovative approaches. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 8(7).
6. Xudoynazarov, E. M. (2019). Didactic possibilities of oral exercises in forming initial classes pupils' mathematical thinking activity. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, Ausgabe. Germany, (1-2019), 249.
7. Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). Boshlang 'ich ta'limda mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. *Молодые ученые*, 1(13), 32-37.
8. Эгамберган, X. М. (2023). Ўқувчиларда танқидий фикрлашни ривожлантиришнинг педагогик ва методик асослари. *Zamonaviy fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish muammolarining innovatsion yechimlari*, 4, 56-59.